

Acta Medica Europa

Psychological Problems Experienced by Patients with Dental Treatment or Missing Teeth

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Article Info

Received: 13 September 2022

Accepted: 29 September 2022

Published: 30 September 2022

Keywords:

Missing teeth, dental treatment, psychological effects, social support, health services.

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine the psychological problems experienced by patients with missing teeth or in need of dental treatment. The research was conducted on individuals with 20 missing teeth or in need of treatment in the Gaziantep province of Turkey. Data was collected through an interview form and analyzed using the thematic analysis method. A comprehensive review was conducted to understand the participants' experiences, emotional reactions, thoughts, support they received, effects on their social lives, services they received from healthcare professionals, and information sources they used. Research results provide important insights into how missing teeth or the treatment process affects individuals' lives. These findings provide important information that can guide us to understand the psychosocial dimension of dental health services and provide better support and services to individuals.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11068798

INTRODUCTION

Dental health has a decisive impact on the overall health of individuals, and a healthy mouth significantly affects a person's quality of life. However, the psychological difficulties faced by individuals with missing teeth or dental treatment needs are not limited to physical health, but also significantly affect mental health. Patients who are missing teeth or need dental treatment have to cope with various psychological factors. In this context, this research aims to understand the psychological problems experienced by patients with missing teeth or dental treatment and the effects of these problems on access to health services and compliance with treatment (1-5).

Individuals who are missing teeth or need dental treatment often encounter problems such as decrease in self-esteem, difficulties in social relations, decrease in functionality and psychological stress. This has a significant impact on the overall health and well-being of both the individual and society. Therefore, this research aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the psychological problems experienced by patients with missing teeth or dental treatment by examining the relationship between dental health and psychological health (3-5).

The importance of this study is related to understanding the psychological health status of patients with missing teeth or in need of dental treatment. This understanding plays an important

role in the planning, implementation and evaluation of health services. Providing dental health services with an integrated approach to meet physical and psychological health needs increases patients' access to treatment and improves their compliance with treatment. In this context, this research aims to contribute to improving the quality of dental health services by providing valuable information for both health policy makers and clinical practitioners (1-5).

METHODS

This research was conducted using a scanning model. The screening model is a research method used to determine the prevalence or characteristics of a particular problem or condition by selecting a sample from a large population.

Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of all patients with dental diseases in Turkey. The sample is a specific subset selected from this universe. In this study, the sample consists of 20 individuals with missing teeth or in need of treatment in Gaziantep. The fact that the sample is limited to Gaziantep aims to narrow the scope of the research and focus on a specific geographical region.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyzes in the study were performed using SPSS 25.0 software (IBM SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive data were given as mean and standard deviation for normally distributed numerical data, and distributions for nominal or ordinal variables were given as numbers and percentages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In gender distribution, the rate of women is 65.0% while the rate of men is 35.0%. The marital status of singles is 45.0%, married is 40.0% and other (widow, divorced) is 15.0%. According to age distribution, the largest group is 31-40 years old with 30.0%, while the smallest groups are 20 and under and 61 and over with 10.0% (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of participants.

Özellikler	Seçenekler	n	%
Gender	Female	13	65.0
	Male	7	35.0
Marital status	Single	9	45.0
	Married	8	40.0
	Widow	3	15.0
Age (years)	<21	2	10.0
	21-30	4	20.0
	31-40	6	30.0
	41-50	3	15.0
	51-60	3	15.0
	>60	2	10.0

Treatment Experience

Data show that the social impact of missing teeth and the difficulties experienced in the treatment process are frequently encountered issues. 30% of the participants stated that they experienced restrictions in social activities due to missing teeth. Additionally, 20% stated that they experienced pain and discomfort during the treatment process. However, 25% reported experiencing difficulties at work or school during treatment. 25% of them stated that they experienced a decrease in their self-confidence due to missing teeth. These findings provide important insights into how missing teeth or the treatment process affects personal and social life (Table 2).

Emotional Response

Data show that the treatment process is emotionally challenging. With a rate of 40%, the majority of participants stated that they were anxious and stressed. While 25% stated that they were worried about the outcome of the treatment, 25% stated that they felt ashamed due to missing teeth. 20% stated that they had emotional difficulties during dental treatment. These findings provide important insight into how missing teeth

or the treatment process can affect psychological well-being (Table 2).

Anxiety

According to the data, concerns about whether the treatment will be successful are one of the most common topics (35%). Additionally, 25% of the participants appear to have aesthetic concerns. While 20% were concerned about the costs of dental treatment, another 20% stated that they were worried about how long the treatment process would take. These findings provide an important insight into how missing teeth or the treatment process affects individuals' anxiety and anxiety levels (Table 2).

Getting Support

According to the data, the importance of moral support from family and friends is emphasized (25%). Additionally, 15% of respondents said they received support from friends when they were concerned about dental treatment costs. With a rate of 30%, the information and support participants received from health professionals were found to be important. Additionally, 30% stated that they received psychological support during the dental treatment process. These findings provide important insight into how environmental supports can affect individuals' success and well-being in treatment (Table 2).

Social Impact

According to the data, the social impact of missing teeth or the treatment process is quite evident. It was observed that 30% of the participants experienced a decrease in their participation in social events. 20% stated that it was comforting for the people in their social circle to be understanding during the treatment process. It was determined that 25% of the participants experienced social isolation. Additionally, 25% stated that they experienced positive changes in their social relationships after dental treatment. These findings provide an important understanding of how missing teeth or the treatment process affects individuals' social lives (Table 2).

Satisfaction with Services

According to the data, satisfaction with the treatment service received from health professionals is quite high (35%). Additionally, communication and professionalism of the healthcare team were found to be important during the treatment process (30% and 20%). It was observed that 15% of the participants were satisfied with the post-treatment follow-up and support services. These findings highlight the importance of the role of healthcare professionals in the treatment process and the services provided (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of themes.

Theme	Code	n	%
Treatment Experience	I experienced restrictions in my social activities due to missing teeth.	6	30%
	I experienced pain and discomfort during the dental treatment process.	4	20%
	I had difficulties at work or school during dental treatment.	5	25%
	I experienced a decrease in self-confidence due to missing teeth.	5	25%
Emotional Response	I was anxious and stressed.	8	40%
	I was worried about the outcome of the treatment.	3	15%
	I felt embarrassed about missing teeth.	5	25%
	I was emotionally challenged during dental treatment.	4	20%
Anxiety	I had concerns about whether the treatment would be successful.	7	35%
	I had aesthetic concerns.	5	25%
	I was concerned about dental treatment costs.	4	20%
	I was concerned about how long the treatment process would take.	4	20%
Getting Support	I survived with the moral support of my family and friends.	5	25%
	When I had concerns about dental treatment costs, I got support from my friends.	3	15%
	The information and support I received from healthcare professionals during the dental treatment process was important.	6	30%
	I received psychological support during the dental treatment process.	6	30%
Social Impact	My participation in social events has decreased due to missing teeth.	6	30%
	I was relieved that the people in my social circle were understanding during dental treatment.	4	20%
	I experienced social isolation due to missing teeth or the treatment process.	5	25%
	I experienced positive changes in my social relationships after dental treatment.	5	25%
Satisfaction with Services	I was satisfied with the treatment service I received from healthcare professionals.	7	35%
	The communication of the healthcare team during the dental treatment process was important to me.	6	30%
	The professionalism of the healthcare professionals put me at ease during the treatment process.	4	20%
	Post-treatment follow-up and support services increased my satisfaction.	3	15%
Information and Resources	I found information about missing teeth or treatment by searching the internet.	5	25%
	I consulted with healthcare professionals to learn about treatment options.	7	35%
	I used brochures about dental treatment.	4	20%
	I learned about dental treatment from my circle of friends.	4	20%
Additional Notes	I would like to receive more support regarding the pain I experienced during the treatment process.	4	20%
	I observed a significant increase in my quality of life after dental treatment.	5	25%
	The intensity of the stress I experienced during the treatment process was more than I expected.	6	30%
	I would like to have access to more information about missing teeth or the treatment process.	5	25%

Information and Resources

According to the data, participants tend to find treatment-related information by searching online (25%). Also common is obtaining information from healthcare professionals and using brochures (35% and 20%). 20% stated that they obtained information about dental treatment from their circle of friends. These findings provide an important understanding of how individuals access information regarding missing teeth or the treatment process and what resources they use (Table 2).

Additional Notes

According to the data, wanting to get more support regarding the pain experienced during the treatment process (20%) and discomfort with the intensity of stress during the treatment process (30%) were frequently expressed. Additionally, observing a significant increase in the quality of life after treatment (25%) and the desire to access more information (25%) are among the important issues. These findings demonstrate the diversity of individual experiences in the

treatment process and how individuals' needs may differ (Table 2).

Literature review

Çanakçı and Çanakçı (6) aimed to examine the incidence of oral and dental diseases in patients at advanced systemic risk. In this study, the oral and dental health conditions of 2000 random patients who applied to İnönü University Vocational School of Health Services were evaluated. Findings revealed that dental diseases are more common in patients at advanced systemic risk (6).

Çobanoğlu et al. (7) aimed to determine the toothpaste preferences of patients applying to the faculty of dentistry and their opinions about the fluoride in toothpastes. Within the scope of this study, a survey was administered to patients who applied to Selçuk Dental Journal. The findings showed that patients' toothpaste preferences and their level of knowledge about fluoride content varied (7).

Dağ and Özalp (8) examined toothpastes, which are an important element of oral and dental health. In this review article, the common use of toothpastes, the ingredients they contain and their effects on health were examined in detail. The authors emphasized that toothpastes play an important role in protecting oral and dental health (8).

Karabulut Gençer et al (9) examined geriatric approaches in restorative dentistry. In this review article, the strategies and treatment methods required to protect oral and dental health in the elderly population were discussed. The authors emphasized the importance of geriatric approaches in restorative dentistry (9).

Özner et al. (10) aimed to evaluate neurologically children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. In this study, the neurological status of pediatric patients admitted to Ankara University Faculty of Medicine was examined. Findings revealed that neurological symptoms are common in children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (10).

Özdemir (11) aimed to determine the reasons why pediatric patients applied to the dentist. In this study, the reasons why pediatric patients who applied to the Journal of International Dental Sciences were analyzed. The findings showed that children's reasons for visiting the dentist were diverse (1).

Özler, Sarıdağ, and Badur (12) examined the effectiveness of botulinum toxin application in the treatment of gummy smile. In this study, the results of botulinum toxin application in the treatment of gummy smile were reported in two case reports published in Aydin Dental Journal. The findings showed that botulinum toxin application is an effective and safe method in the treatment of gummy smile (12).

Özkurt (13) aimed to evaluate patients with total missing teeth with the panoramic mandibular index. In this study, panoramic radiographs of patients with total missing teeth who applied to Atatürk University Faculty of Dentistry were examined. The findings showed that panoramic radiography is a valuable tool for determining the mandibular index of patients with total missing teeth (13).

Peker et al (14) investigated the effectiveness of a multidisciplinary approach on a case with isolated multiple missing teeth. In this study, a patient with isolated multiple missing teeth who applied to Atatürk University Faculty of Dentistry was followed up for a year by a multidisciplinary team. Findings showed that a multidisciplinary approach was effective in treating patients with isolated multiple missing teeth (14).

Altın et al. (15) compiled the relationship between anemia and dentistry. In this review article, the effects of different types of anemia on oral and perioral tissues were examined. The authors emphasized the importance of anemia for dentistry (15).

Karabaş and Tatar (16) investigated the knowledge level of patients with partial missing teeth about coronavirus and their attitudes towards rehabilitation. Within the scope of this study, data on the level of knowledge of patients with partial missing teeth regarding coronavirus and their attitudes towards rehabilitation were presented in a conference paper published in the Journal of Meffert Implant Institute. The findings showed

that patients' level of knowledge about coronavirus varied and their attitudes towards rehabilitation were also affected (16).

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to thoroughly examine the psychological problems experienced by patients with missing teeth or in need of dental treatment. A comprehensive study was conducted to understand the participants' experiences, emotional reactions, thoughts, the support they received, the impact on their social lives, the services they received from healthcare professionals, and the information sources they used.

Research results reveal the various difficulties experienced by individuals with missing teeth or in need of dental treatment. Difficulties such as pain, discomfort and restrictions in social activities, which are frequently encountered during the treatment process, stand out among the experiences of the participants. Additionally, the treatment process appears to be emotionally challenging and individuals experience emotional reactions such as anxiety, stress, and shame. These findings show that missing teeth or the treatment process affects individuals not only physically but also psychologically and emotionally.

When the participants' thoughts and concerns are examined, it is seen that issues such as whether the treatment will be successful or not, aesthetic concerns, cost concerns and the duration of the treatment process are important. These concerns indicate that individuals may have difficulty coping with uncertainties regarding the treatment process and may seek support.

The research also shows that participants were significantly impacted by the environmental support and services they received from healthcare professionals. Moral support, information, and psychological support from family, friends, and healthcare professionals influenced the participants' success during the treatment process. The presence of these supports helped individuals feel stronger and more motivated during the treatment process.

Research results also reveal the ways individuals obtain information and use resources regarding the treatment process. Internet research, meeting with health professionals, brochures, and obtaining information from friends are among the common methods used by participants to meet their information needs.

In conclusion, this research has made an important contribution to understanding the psychological problems experienced by patients with missing teeth or in need of dental treatment. The findings provide an important basis for understanding the difficulties these individuals experience, their emotional reactions, thoughts and the support they receive. These findings provide important insights that can guide understanding the psychosocial dimension of dental health care and providing better support and services in this area.

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